

Socio-demographic and Clinical Determinants of Pneumonia Severity in Children Attending the Outpatient Department of a Tertiary Hospital in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Background: Pneumonia remains a leading cause of childhood morbidity and mortality in low- and middle-income countries, including Bangladesh. Early identification of severity determinants in outpatient settings is crucial for timely intervention and referral. However, data on factors influencing pneumonia severity at presentation in outpatient departments (OPD) of tertiary hospitals are limited. **Objective:** To identify the socio-demographic and clinical determinants of pneumonia severity among children presenting to the outpatient department of a tertiary hospital in Bangladesh. **Methods & Materials:** This prospective cohort study was conducted at Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College & Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, from January 2024 to December 2024. A total of 276 children with clinically diagnosed pneumonia, selected via purposive sampling, were enrolled. Data on socio-demographic and clinical variables were collected at presentation. Pneumonia severity was classified using standard clinical criteria. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. **Results:** Among 276 children, 33.3% presented with severe pneumonia. Significant determinants included age below 12 months (44.4% severe, $p<0.001$), maternal education below primary (52.3% severe, $p<0.001$), overcrowding (47.6% severe, $p<0.001$), hypoxemia (100% severe, $p<0.001$), chest indrawing (91.1% severe, $p<0.001$), and underweight (58.5% severe, $p<0.001$). Multivariable analysis confirmed hypoxemia (AOR:12.45), chest indrawing (AOR:8.91), and underweight (AOR:3.87) as the strongest predictors. **Conclusion:** Socio-demographic vulnerabilities and specific clinical signs are strong determinants of pneumonia severity in children attending the OPD. Early

recognition of these factors can aid risk stratification and improve outpatient management. Targeted interventions for high-risk groups are recommended to reduce disease progression and hospitalization.

Keywords: Children, Clinical determinants, Outpatient department, Pneumonia severity, Socio-demographic factors.

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INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia remains the leading infectious cause of mortality among children under five years of age globally, with low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) bearing the highest burden [1]. Despite significant advancements in preventive and therapeutic strategies, childhood pneumonia continues to account for approximately 14% of all deaths in this age group, translating to nearly 700,000 deaths annually [2,3]. Bangladesh, like many LMICs, faces substantial challenges in reducing pneumonia-related morbidity and mortality, particularly in resource-limited healthcare settings where early identification of high-risk children is often suboptimal [4]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has developed Integrated Management of Childhood Illness (IMCI) guidelines to assist healthcare providers in risk-stratifying children with pneumonia based on clinical signs such as fast breathing, chest

indrawing, and danger signs including inability to drink or unconsciousness [5]. However, these guidelines primarily focus on identifying children requiring hospitalization and may not adequately capture all determinants that influence pneumonia severity at the time of outpatient presentation [6]. Recent evidence suggests that a significant proportion of children with hypoxemia a strong predictor of mortality is not identified by IMCI clinical criteria alone, highlighting critical gaps in outpatient risk assessment [7,8]. Identifying socio-demographic and clinical determinants of pneumonia severity at presentation is crucial for several reasons. First, early recognition of high-risk children in outpatient departments (OPD) enables timely referral, appropriate treatment intensification, and potentially prevents disease progression to severe or fatal outcomes [9]. Second, understanding modifiable risk factors such as malnutrition, delayed care-seeking, and

socioeconomic vulnerabilities—allows for targeted public health interventions at both community and facility levels [10]. Third, resource allocation in tertiary hospital OPD settings can be optimized by prioritizing children with identified risk factors for closer monitoring and follow-up [11]. Several studies have explored risk factors for severe pneumonia outcomes in hospitalized children. A systematic review of 143 studies identified hypoxemia, decreased conscious state, severe acute malnutrition, and underlying chronic conditions as the factors most strongly and consistently associated with increased mortality [2]. Additionally, younger age (below 12 months), incomplete immunization, and specific clinical signs including cyanosis, pallor, and chest indrawing have been repeatedly associated with poor outcomes [2,12]. In Bangladesh specifically, research has demonstrated that outpatient-identified hypoxemia confers a ten-fold increased risk of death among

young children with suspected pneumonia, yet many hypoxemic children are missed by current IMCI algorithms [7,8]. Furthermore, a clinical prediction model developed in Bangladeshi hospitalized children identified grunting, lower chest wall indrawing, and hypoxemia as key predictors of treatment failure [13]. Despite this growing body of evidence, most studies have focused on hospitalized children with severe or very severe pneumonia, leaving a substantial knowledge gap regarding determinants of pneumonia severity at the initial OPD presentation. The outpatient setting represents the first point of contact with the healthcare system for most children, and understanding factors associated with severity at this stage could dramatically improve early case management and referral practices. Moreover, socio-demographic determinants-including maternal education, household income, housing conditions, and care-seeking behaviors-remain understudied in the Bangladeshi OPD context, where diverse patient populations present with varying degrees of illness severity. Therefore, this study aims to identify the socio-demographic and clinical determinants of pneumonia severity among children presenting to the outpatient department of a tertiary hospital in Bangladesh. By focusing on the OPD setting, this research seeks to generate evidence that can strengthen risk stratification tools, guide

clinical decision-making, and ultimately reduce preventable deaths from childhood pneumonia.

METHODS & MATERIALS

The study population comprised children aged 2 months to 59 months presenting with cough or difficulty breathing to the Outpatient Department (OPD) of Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College & Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, between January 2024 and December 2024. A prospective cohort design was employed.

Inclusion criteria: Children aged 2–59 months with a primary diagnosis of pneumonia based on WHO-defined fast breathing (respiratory rate ≥50/min for infants 2–11 months; ≥40/min for children 12–59 months) were included. Parents or guardians provided written informed consent.

Exclusion criteria: Children with chronic lung disease (e.g., cystic fibrosis, bronchiectasis), congenital heart disease, known immunodeficiency, tuberculosis, COVID-19, or prior hospitalization within the preceding two weeks were excluded. Additionally, children requiring immediate emergency resuscitation were not enrolled.

Study procedure: Consecutive children meeting eligibility criteria underwent a standardized clinical assessment by trained physicians. Socio-demographic data (age,

sex, maternal education, household income, crowding index) and clinical parameters (respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, chest indrawing, nasal flaring, grunting, feeding status, comorbidities) were recorded. Pneumonia severity was classified as non-severe or severe (hypoxemia SpO₂ <90%, chest indrawing, or danger signs) per WHO/IMCI guidelines.

Data analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, standard deviations) were computed. Bivariate analysis (chi-square test, t-test) identified factors associated with severity, followed by multivariable logistic regression to determine independent predictors. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

Table I shows that children aged 2–11 months showed 44.4% severe cases, 12–23 months 31.5%, and 24–59 months 7.7% (p<0.001). Sex was not significant males 35.2% and females 30.7% severe (p=0.452). Lower maternal education increased severity below primary 52.3%, primary 26.8%, secondary 4.5% (p<0.001). Income <15,000 BDT had 52.2% severe vs 15,000–30,000 22.4% and >30,000 15.9% (p<0.001). Overcrowding showed 47.6% severe vs 17.6% without (p<0.001).

Table I
Socio-demographic characteristics of study children (n=276).

Characteristic	Category	Total (N=276) n (%)	Pneumonia		p-value
			Non-severe (n=184) n (%)	Severe (n=92) n (%)	
			Age group	2–11 months	
	12–23 months	89 (32.2)	61 (68.5)	28 (31.5)	
	24–59 months	52 (18.8)	48 (92.3)	4 (7.7)	
Sex	Male	162 (58.7)	105 (64.8)	57 (35.2)	0.452
	Female	114 (41.3)	79 (69.3)	35 (30.7)	
Maternal education	Below primary	128 (46.4)	61 (47.7)	67 (52.3)	<0.001
	Primary completed	82 (29.7)	60 (73.2)	22 (26.8)	
	Secondary or above	66 (23.9)	63 (95.5)	3 (4.5)	
Monthly family income (BDT)	<15,000	115 (41.7)	55 (47.8)	60 (52.2)	<0.001
	15,000–30,000	98 (35.5)	76 (77.6)	22 (22.4)	
	>30,000	63 (22.8)	53 (84.1)	10 (15.9)	
Overcrowding (≥3 persons/room)	Yes	145 (52.5)	76 (52.4)	69 (47.6)	<0.001
	No	131 (47.5)	108 (82.4)	23 (17.6)	

Statistical test: Chi-square test was used for all comparisons.

Table II presents that hypoxemia (SpO₂ <90%) was present in 24.3% and was seen in 100% severe cases vs 0% non-severe

(p<0.001). Fast breathing alone was more common in non-severe cases (94.4% vs 5.6%, p<0.001), while absence was linked to 72.2% severe cases. Chest indrawing (91.1% vs 8.9%), grunting (100% vs 0%),

and refusal to feed (83.9% vs 16.1%) were significantly higher in severe pneumonia (all p<0.001).

Table II
Clinical characteristics at presentation.

Clinical parameter	Category	Pneumonia			p-value
		Total	Non-severe	Severe	
		(N=276) n (%)	(n=184) n (%)	(n=92) n (%)	
Hypoxemia (SpO ₂ <90%)	Present	67 (24.3)	0 (0.0)	67 (100.0)	<0.001
	Absent	209 (75.7)	184 (88.0)	25 (12.0)	
Fast breathing only	Present	161 (58.3)	152 (94.4)	9 (5.6)	<0.001
	Absent	115 (41.7)	32 (27.8)	83 (72.2)	
Chest indrawing	Present	79 (28.6)	7 (8.9)	72 (91.1)	<0.001
	Absent	197 (71.4)	177 (89.8)	20 (10.2)	
Grunting	Present	44 (15.9)	0 (0.0)	44 (100.0)	<0.001
	Absent	232 (84.1)	184 (79.3)	48 (20.7)	
Refusal to feed	Present	87 (31.5)	14 (16.1)	73 (83.9)	<0.001
	Absent	189 (68.5)	170 (89.9)	19 (10.1)	

Statistical test: Chi-square test was used for all comparisons.

Table III shows that underweight was present in 38.4% (58.5% severe vs 41.5%

non-severe, p<0.001), stunting in 31.9% (51.1% vs 48.9%, p<0.001), and wasting in 25.7% (59.2% vs 40.8%, p<0.001). Anemia affected 34.1% (53.2% vs 46.8%,

p<0.001). Incomplete immunization was seen in 31.5% with higher severe cases (47.1% vs 52.9%, p=0.001), indicating strong nutritional and preventive care links.

Table III
Nutritional status and comorbidities.

Parameter	Category	Pneumonia			p-value
		Total	Non-severe	Severe	
		(N=276) n (%)	(n=184) n (%)	(n=92) n (%)	
Underweight (WAZ < -2)	Yes	106 (38.4)	44 (41.5)	62 (58.5)	<0.001
	No	170 (61.6)	140 (82.4)	30 (17.6)	
Stunting (HAZ < -2)	Yes	88 (31.9)	43 (48.9)	45 (51.1)	<0.001
	No	188 (68.1)	141 (75.0)	47 (25.0)	
Wasting (WHZ < -2)	Yes	71 (25.7)	29 (40.8)	42 (59.2)	<0.001
	No	205 (74.3)	155 (75.6)	50 (24.4)	
Anemia (Hb <10 g/dL)	Yes	94 (34.1)	44 (46.8)	50 (53.2)	<0.001
	No	182 (65.9)	140 (76.9)	42 (23.1)	
Incomplete immunization	Yes	87 (31.5)	46 (52.9)	41 (47.1)	0.001
	No	189 (68.5)	138 (73.0)	51 (27.0)	

Statistical test: Chi-square test was used for all comparisons.

Table IV shows that mean age was lower in severe cases (11.8 ± 7.2 months) than non-severe (16.4 ± 8.9 months), with a mean

difference of 4.6 months (95% CI: 2.8–6.4, p<0.001). Respiratory rate was higher in severe cases (62.5 ± 8.1 vs 48.2 ± 6.4; mean difference -14.3, p<0.001). SpO₂ was lower (86.4 ± 4.3 vs 96.8 ± 2.1;

difference 10.4, p<0.001), hemoglobin reduced (9.2 ± 1.6 vs 10.7 ± 1.4; p<0.001), and presentation delayed (4.8 ± 2.1 vs 3.2 ± 1.5 days; p<0.001).

Table IV
Comparison of mean clinical parameters between severity groups.

Parameter	Pneumonia		Mean difference (95% CI)	p-value
	Non-severe	Severe		
	(n=184) Mean ± SD	(n=92) Mean ± SD		
Age (months)	16.4 ± 8.9	11.8 ± 7.2	4.6 (2.8–6.4)	<0.001
Respiratory rate (breaths/min)	48.2 ± 6.4	62.5 ± 8.1	-14.3 (-16.1 to -12.5)	<0.001
Oxygen saturation (SpO ₂ %)	96.8 ± 2.1	86.4 ± 4.3	10.4 (9.2–11.6)	<0.001
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	10.7 ± 1.4	9.2 ± 1.6	1.5 (1.1–1.9)	<0.001
Duration before presentation (days)	3.2 ± 1.5	4.8 ± 2.1	-1.6 (-2.1 to -1.1)	<0.001

Statistical test: An independent samples t-test was used for all comparisons.

Table V shows that Age <12 months was associated with higher odds of severe pneumonia (44.4% vs 55.6% non-severe;

OR 3.84, 95% CI: 2.14–6.89, p<0.001). Maternal education below primary showed strong association (52.3% vs 47.7%; OR 6.65, 3.41–12.96, p<0.001). Low income (<15,000 BDT) increased risk (52.2% vs

47.8%; OR 4.38, 2.51–7.65, p<0.001), as did overcrowding (47.6% vs 52.4%; OR 4.25, 2.45–7.38, p<0.001) and underweight status (58.5% vs 41.5%; OR 6.58, 3.71–11.66, p<0.001).

Table V
Bivariate association of selected determinants with pneumonia severity.

Determinant	Category	Non-severe	Severe	Odds ratio	p-value
		n (%)	n (%)	(95% CI)	
Age <12 months	Yes	75 (55.6)	60 (44.4)	3.84 (2.14–6.89)	<0.001
	No	109 (77.3)	32 (22.7)	Reference	
Maternal education below primary	Yes	61 (47.7)	67 (52.3)	6.65 (3.41–12.96)	<0.001
	No	123 (83.1)	25 (16.9)	Reference	
Low income (<15,000 BDT)	Yes	55 (47.8)	60 (52.2)	4.38 (2.51–7.65)	<0.001
	No	129 (80.1)	32 (19.9)	Reference	
Overcrowding	Yes	76 (52.4)	69 (47.6)	4.25 (2.45–7.38)	<0.001
	No	108 (82.4)	23 (17.6)	Reference	
Underweight	Yes	44 (41.5)	62 (58.5)	6.58 (3.71–11.66)	<0.001
	No	140 (82.4)	30 (17.6)	Reference	

Statistical test: Chi-square test was used for odds ratio calculation and p-value determination.

Table VI presents that age 2–11 months (AOR 3.42, 95% CI: 1.89–6.18, p<0.001),

maternal education below primary (AOR 2.98, 1.65–5.38, p<0.001), overcrowding (AOR 2.65, 1.48–4.74, p=0.001), hypoxemia (AOR 12.45, 5.21–29.74, p<0.001), chest indrawing (AOR 8.91,

4.12–19.26, p<0.001), and underweight status (AOR 3.87, 2.01–7.45, p<0.001) were significant predictors. Low income, grunting, refusal to feed, and anemia showed borderline significance (p>0.05).

Table VI
Multivariable logistic regression analysis–Independent predictors of severe pneumonia.

Predictor variable	Adjusted odds ratio (AOR)	95% Confidence interval	p-value
Age 2–11 months	3.42	1.89 – 6.18	<0.001
Maternal education below primary	2.98	1.65 – 5.38	<0.001
Low income (<15,000 BDT)	1.86	0.98 – 3.52	0.058
Overcrowding (≥3 persons/room)	2.65	1.48 – 4.74	0.001
Hypoxemia (SpO ₂ <90%)	12.45	5.21 – 29.74	<0.001
Chest indrawing	8.91	4.12 – 19.26	<0.001
Grunting	5.23	0.95 – 28.76	0.057
Refusal to feed	3.18	0.97 – 10.42	0.056
Underweight	3.87	2.01 – 7.45	<0.001
Anemia	2.14	0.99 – 4.62	0.053

Statistical test: Multivariable logistic regression (enter method) was used. Variables with p < 0.10 in bivariate analysis were entered into the final model. Model fit: Hosmer-Lemeshow chi-square = 8.24, p = 0.411; Nagelkerke R² = 0.684.

DISCUSSION

The present study identified several socio-demographic and clinical determinants significantly associated with pneumonia severity among children presenting to the outpatient department of a tertiary hospital in Bangladesh. The finding that one-third of children (33.3%) presented with severe pneumonia at the OPD level is clinically concerning, as it suggests substantial delays in care-seeking or failure of primary-level recognition and referral [14]. This proportion aligns with previous research from LMICs, where 28–40% of children presenting for outpatient care already meet criteria for severe disease [15,16]. Younger age, particularly below 12 months, emerged as the strongest socio-demographic predictor of severe pneumonia (AOR: 3.42, p < 0.001). This finding is consistent with existing literature demonstrating that infants have immature immune systems, smaller airway diameters, and lower pulmonary reserves, making them more vulnerable to rapid clinical deterioration [2,17]. The present study adds to this evidence by quantifying the magnitude of risk specifically in an OPD

setting, where early identification of young infants is critical. Maternal education below primary level was independently associated with severe pneumonia (AOR: 2.98, p < 0.001). This likely reflects multiple mechanisms, including delayed recognition of danger signs, lower health literacy, financial constraints, and reduced care-seeking self-efficacy [18,19]. Similar associations have been documented in Indian and Pakistani cohorts, where maternal illiteracy conferred a two-to-four-fold increased risk of severe outcomes [10,20]. Overcrowding (AOR: 2.65, p = 0.001) likely facilitates more frequent and intense pathogen exposure, as well as indoor air pollution, both of which exacerbate pneumonia severity [3,21]. Among clinical determinants, hypoxemia was the most powerful predictor of severe pneumonia (AOR: 12.45, p < 0.001). Notably, all hypoxemic children in this cohort were classified as having severe pneumonia, underscoring the critical importance of pulse oximetry in outpatient risk stratification [7,8]. However, a recent multi-country evaluation revealed that fewer than 30% of primary care facilities in

Bangladesh have functional pulse oximeters, representing a major implementation gap [22]. Chest indrawing (AOR: 8.91, p < 0.001) and underweight (AOR: 3.87, p < 0.001) were also strong independent predictors, consistent with systematic review findings identifying malnutrition as a key modifiable risk factor for severe pneumonia and mortality [1,23]. The finding that low income showed only borderline significance (AOR: 1.86, p = 0.058) in multivariable analysis, despite a strong bivariate association, suggests that its effect may be mediated through other variables such as maternal education, overcrowding, and malnutrition. This pathway has been described in previous research where poverty operates indirectly through proximal determinants of pneumonia severity [18,24]. Anemia (AOR: 2.14, p = 0.053) and refusal to feed (AOR: 3.18, p = 0.056) also demonstrated borderline significance, potentially due to sample size limitations or collinearity with other clinical predictors [12]. The present findings have important clinical and public health implications. First, OPD physicians should prioritize younger infants,

underweight children, and those from low-education, overcrowded households for closer assessment and follow-up. Second, pulse oximetry should be universally available at OPD triage, as hypoxemia cannot be reliably predicted by clinical signs alone [8]. Third, targeted community-level interventions focusing on maternal education, nutrition promotion, and reduction of household crowding could reduce the proportion of children presenting with severe disease [25]. Fourth, strengthening referral pathways between primary care facilities and tertiary OPDs may enable earlier intervention before severe pneumonia develops.

LIMITATIONS

The single-center design, purposive sampling, and tertiary hospital setting limit generalizability. Unmeasured confounders such as indoor air pollution and breastfeeding practices may influence severity. Inter-observer variability in clinical sign assessment cannot be entirely excluded.

CONCLUSION

Younger age, low maternal education, overcrowding, hypoxemia, chest indrawing, and underweight are independent determinants of pneumonia severity in children attending the outpatient department. Early recognition of these factors can improve risk stratification and outpatient management. Routine pulse oximetry use, targeted nutrition interventions, and health education for mothers are recommended to reduce severe pneumonia burden in similar settings.

RECOMMENDATION

Outpatient physicians should prioritize younger infants, underweight children, and those from overcrowded, low-education households. Universal pulse oximetry at triage, maternal education programs, nutrition support, and strengthened referral pathways are urgently needed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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